

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Pitch Estimation of Choir Music using Deep Learning Strategies: from Solo to Unison Recordings

Helena Cuesta

Supervisor: Dr. Emilia Gómez

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To my soon-to-be born niece/nephew.

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Abstract

The goals of this thesis are the creation of new datasets to study aspects of choir singing, focusing on unison performances, and to research on data-driven methods for the automatic pitch estimation of *a cappella* choir singing performances. Choral music is polyphonic and involves multiple singers typically grouped into four main voices (soprano, alto, tenor and bass). The task of multi-pitch estimation becomes challenging due to the variety of acoustic scenarios (from solo singers to big choirs) and the lack of annotated datasets for training and evaluation, especially for the polyphonic case. In particular, we focus on building models of pitch from monophonic and unison recordings. In order to do that, we first build a dataset of choir singing that contains different types of performances: solo singers, unison, and four parts choir. Then, we train several deep learning architectures to extract pitch information from monophonic singing voice signals, and adapt them afterwards to model unison performances.

The models for monophonic pitch estimation achieve state-of-the-art performances, and in some cases we outperform some of them, especially for the mid-frequency range. The model for unison choir is capable of predicting the average pitch and its dispersion of a unison performance with an average accuracy of 70%, although its accuracy and generalization capabilities are limited by the size of the dataset.

The presented models provide a first step towards de automatic transcription of choir singing recordings, and the unison model is a useful resource for choir singing synthesis.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Singing in a choir is a way to express emotion and connect with other singers that humans have been using for a long time. Choir singing affects the quality of life in a positive way, and improves social integration. Choral music and singing have been studied from many different perspectives, e.g. physiological, musicological..., but there are very few studies that work both with choirs and technology. This is the aim of the CASAS (Community-Assisted Singing Analysis and Synthesis) project: try to combine Music Information Retrieval (MIR) tasks and Singing Voice Processing and Synthesis to develop new technologies for choir singing practice¹. The present work will be developed in the scope of the CASAS project, dealing basically with pitch estimation of *a cappella* recordings.

1.1 Context

The CASAS (Community-Assisted Singing Analysis and Synthesis) project is developed in the the Music Information Research (MIR) lab of the Music Technology Group (MTG) at Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF) in Barcelona and tries to exploit MIR and singing voice processing techniques to develop technologies to assist singers in their musical practice and to enhance the public-domain choral music archives.

Singers and audiences have limited access to choral music, especially classical music: although these resources are becoming digital nowadays, there is still a lack of public-domain archives of this kind of music. Given the amount of available state-of-the-art technologies related to music processing, analysis, and description, it seems appropriate to exploit them to create new digital tools, resources, and repositories for real-world applications, focusing in choir singing practice.

At the same time, there are also massive digital music collections, where both mu-

¹CASAS: Community-Assisted Singing Analysis and Synthesis. <http://mtg.upf.edu/projects/casas>

music scores and recordings coexist (Choral Public Domain Library², Petrucci Music Library³). The web provides an infinite number of new possibilities regarding music archives, but this also means that we need to handle data properly and have as much information as possible. MIR techniques are very relevant for this purpose: tasks such as genre or music emotion classification, might be very useful for automatically tagging music collections, a field which is broadly explored for non-classical music. However, for classical music collections, and specifically for choral music, we find very few attempts to use MIR techniques for music description. An example of these potential applications is automatic transcription of music, i.e. the extraction of a musical score from an audio recording, which could be very useful to automatically obtain scores from recordings in digital repositories of choral music, and it is one of the the final targets of this project.

There are several challenging aspects in the context of automatic transcription of choir singing. One basic step of an automatic transcription algorithm is the extraction of the notes, a process we will call pitch estimation. Existing pitch estimation algorithms are mainly designed to work well in recordings which have a clear leading melody (e.g. lead singer and instrumental accompaniment), but in general, they have a drop in performance when applied to other kind of recordings such as instrumental music where several instruments play different melodies at the same time, symphonic or choral music.

Choir recordings are especially challenging because the voices may have similar pitch contours and the timbre properties may not be different enough to differentiate one voice from the others. In general, current state of the art melody extraction algorithms estimate the soprano part as the main melody, which means that when the soprano voice is not present, they report the fragment as unvoiced (no melody present), while maybe the melody has shifted to one of the other voices. Another limitation of these systems is that they have poor results if the main melody is sung by a voice which is not the soprano.

Similarly, unison performances of a choir are also very challenging in terms of pitch estimation: in a unison performance, all the singers produce the same note at the same time. Octave equivalence is taken into account in such a way that notes which are an octave apart are considered to be unison. These performances are not exactly polyphonic nor monophonic, given that we have several sound sources at the same time. Therefore, pitch estimation algorithms for monophonic signals show a poor performance in these kind of signals due to two main reasons: first, the octave equivalence and second, the fundamental frequency dispersion, which will be discussed in further Sections.

²The Choral Public Domain Library (www.cpd1.org/) is a sheet music archive focused on vocal music.

³The International Music Score Library Project (IMSLP), also known as Petrucci Music Library (<http://imslp.org>), is a virtual library of public-domain music scores. This project is based on subscriptions.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the vocal tract resonator. It transmits sounds from the glottal end to the lip opening. In the resonator stage (the vocal tract), some frequencies are amplified - the formant frequencies. From [2].

1.2 Related Work

This project focuses on automatic transcription of choir music. There are two essential terms: *automatic transcription* and *choir music*. By choir music we mean music performed by a group of either professional or amateur singers, usually organized in the typical choir setting SATB (soprano, alto, tenor, bass), corresponding to note ranges from high to low pitches. According to Benetos et al. [1], automatic transcription is the process of converting audio signals into some symbolic representation, such as scores. We deeply discuss both terms in this Section.

1.2.1 Acoustics of Choir Singing

In his book, Sundberg [2] explains how voice is produced from both the anatomical and physiological points of view, and how speakers and singers model it to obtain different notes, phonemes, articulations or accents. All these aspects are very relevant both for singing voice synthesis and analysis, but before we start with choir music, we first need to understand how a single singing voice works. According to Sundberg, speaking and singing consist of moving our lips, tongue, jaw, and larynx while an airstream coming from the lungs passes the vocal folds [2], making them vibrate. This vibration of the vocal folds is the voice source, and is then passed through the vocal tract, which acts as a resonator. In Figure 1 we display an schematic illustration of the signal flow from its origin in the lungs (initial source) to its end, the lip opening (output). The figure is taken from [2]. In the vocal tract, the formant frequencies are amplified and then the signal is forwarded to the lip opening. In the human vocal tract there are around 4-5 formant frequencies, which are used to shape different vowels. In singing voice, especially in male soloists, there is what is called the singer's format, which is a frequency around 2-3kHz where trained singers use more energy. We will come back to this feature. Given that a choir is a set of individual singers, we could think that modelling a choir performance is simply adding individual singers' models together, but it is not that straightforward. Bonada et al. [3] claim that traditional approaches to choir synthesis are usually either based on transformation of solo voice recordings or by the generation of multiple clones of a single voice. Even though each of the clones has small variations in tempo, pitch,

and timbre, these synthesized choirs sound very artificial. Additionally, they also talk about approaches which use small segments of actual choir recordings and concatenate them. This results in very poor phonetic transitions because the samples are mainly allophone (i.e. one single speech sound). However, in their approach, which is called Unisong, they use concatenation of di-allophones, as well as sample transformations, and claim to obtain much more natural sounds in *a cappella* unison performances⁴.

Sundberg [2] also argues that solo singing and choir singing have several differences. The main one is that the way singers produce their voice when singing in a choir differs from how they do it when singing as soloists. Experiments have shown that soloists, in general, sing louder, and this makes the overtones be louder too, especially the high overtones. Regarding the formant frequencies, a study made by Rossing et al. [4] showed that the energy in the formant frequencies was higher when the same male singer sung as a soloist than when he sung along with a choir.

In addition to this loudness difference, there are also important differences that relate to pitch: the way a singer in a choir produces a specific pitch is affected by how other singers are producing the *same* pitch at the same time (unison). This is the main cause of the fundamental frequency dispersion that we find in unison performances [5]. In such performances, all the members of a choir are supposed to sing the same note, or pitch, at the same time. In singing voice, and according to Sundberg [2], these frequencies are called *phonation frequencies*, and the agreement between all the voice sources, i.e. all the singers, is referred to as *degree of unison*. Different experiments have been made to measure this dispersion in small ensembles of singers. For example, the overview of choir acoustics by Ternström [5] talks about a study that Sacerdote made in 1957 that used an autocorrelation function to measure the F0 dispersion in a recording of four soprano singers. He found this dispersion to be around 130 cents; this large value suggested that the singers were using vibrato in their performance. There are other studies, such as the one by Lottermoser and Meyer, which is discussed both by Sundberg [2] and Ternström [5], in which they used recordings of three different choirs to study how the intonation was in different intervals. They also measured the bandwidth of partials to extract the F0 dispersion, which was found to be around 20-30 cents on average. However, these studies did not take into account voice modulations such as vibrato or inherent voice instabilities.

This F0 dispersion is an essential element to take into account when trying to extract pitch from recordings, especially when there are unison performances: if the dispersion is relatively high, we might have errors. It is also very relevant for choir singing synthesis, because if we took this dispersion into account, the result would sound much more natural. Ternström [6] published a study where he evaluated the

⁴*A cappella* singing is a type of music where the voice is the only source and there is no other instrumental accompaniment. Unison performances are those where all the members of the choir (or orchestra, or ensemble, or any other group of performers) sing or play the same notes (or at a distance of one octave) at the same time.

pitch scatter - pitch dispersion, standard deviation over the voices - in unison choir sounds. In the experiments, instead of using actual live choir recordings, they used singing synthesis techniques to create different choral timbres with different characteristics, i.e. different pitch scatters. Then, several subjects had to listen to the results and evaluate how they perceived these synthetic recordings. They adopted this methodology because they argue that in live choir sounds, the effect known as *flutter*⁵ affects the statistical properties of the sound, meaning that the pitch variations are likely to affect the pitch scatter of the sound. After their experiments, they found that in general, subjects preferred up a 5 cents pitch scatter, while they reported to tolerate up to 14 cents.

In addition to the features that have just been mentioned, when modelling a *cappella* performances one should also take into account the intonation. According to The Oxford Modern English Dictionary, intonation is *the accuracy of pitch in playing or singing, or on a stringed instrument such as a guitar*. When there is an instrumental accompaniment, the singers can follow a clear pitched reference. However, according to Dai et al. [7], in a *cappella* singing the reference pitch is in the singer's memory, and it is likely to change over time. This results in a change in tuning over the duration of the piece. This is called *intonation or pitch drift* and it is usually found as a lowering of pitch. In their study, they explore to which extent the duration of the notes affects the intonation of a *cappella* singing by recording subjects singing short excerpts of well-known songs. The singers were only given the starting note and a metronome with an unpitched sound. They compute the pitch and the intervals, as well as the errors made by the singers as compared to the score of the songs. Then, using a sliding window along the recording, they estimate the local tuning reference (with different windows and window sizes) and compute the pitch errors with respect to the reference. They found that note duration and the tritone interval are likely to have an impact on pitch errors. Additionally, by computing the local pitch reference, they found that some singers showed a random pitch drift and, in other, this drift showed a periodic structure linked to the score (to its repetitions).

The pitch drift phenomenon represents an important issue for automatic transcription, a concept that we discuss in the following subsection.

1.2.2 Automatic Transcription of Music

This task involves several subtasks such as automatic pitch estimation, note segmentation and tracking, and rhythm extraction. While the problem of pitch estimation is considered to be solved for monophonic signals (i.e. one single source) [1][8], polyphonic signals are still very challenging: in a polyphonic audio signal, several sources might be playing different melodies at the same time, following different rhythmic patterns, and in many cases with similar timbres. This means that in the time-frequency domain, the frequency components of one sound are likely to overlap with the components of simultaneous sounds [9].

⁵The *flutter* is produced by small variations in the fundamental frequency that are not perceived as pitch variations but they do not affect the timbre of the sound.

Pitch estimation and melody extraction have been widely studied and there are some approaches that achieve good performances with both monophonic and polyphonic signals. For this project we deal with choir recordings, but we also work with individual voices, so we are interested in methods that perform pitch estimation both in monophonic and polyphonic signals.

We can divide the methods for monophonic pitch estimation into three different classes: time-domain, frequency-domain and data-driven approaches.

Time-domain approaches

The first group uses the audio signal in the time domain (i.e. the audio samples) to obtain some kind of periodicity that shows its fundamental frequency. According to Tzanetakis [10], some examples include the zero-crossing rate (ZCR) or the autocorrelation function (ACF), as well as other methods considered state-of-the-art such as YIN [11], developed by De Cheveigné et al., or pYIN, a probabilistic version of YIN presented by Mauch and Dixon [12]. By using the ZCR we obtain the number of times the signal crosses the 0 (i.e. changes its sign), which provides a simple measure of the frequency content of the signal; however, it is not very robust in noisy conditions. The autocorrelation function shows the points of the signal where it is more similar to itself, which also gives a measure of periodicity, and it is more robust than the ZCR. This is why it is used as a base for more complex methods such as YIN and pYIN. YIN uses the squared difference function between a signal and its delayed version, so that in periodic signals, at every period this function becomes zero. pYIN uses this algorithm together with a probabilistic model that chooses which is the best pitch candidate at each frame, based on probabilities.

Frequency-domain approaches

The frequency-domain approaches use the frequency representation of the audio signal, i.e. the spectrum, to obtain the periodicity information. These methods include the spectral autocorrelation (SAC) function, which is based on the same idea of the ACF but using the spectral content of the signal; spectral pattern matching, which is a method based on templates: we have the templates of the magnitude spectrum of different pitches and even different instruments; then, we compute the spectrum of the input signal and using a matching algorithm we assign the most similar template.

Data-driven approaches

The data-driven approaches, which will be the focus of this project, are those where machine learning algorithms are used to predict pitch. As we will see throughout this text, they are not the most common because a lot of data is necessary to use them, but with the success of neural networks for many different MIR tasks, researchers start to use them. We cite some examples below for the case of polyphonic pitch estimation.

Regarding polyphonic audio signals, and according to the review by Salamon et al. [8], there are two main types of approaches for melody extraction: salience-based methods and source separation based methods. Additionally, there are also some data-driven methods in the literature which do not fit in either of these two categories because they use machine learning techniques. According to Kum & Nam [13], there are two main reasons why very few data-driven approaches i.e. machine learning and classification, have been made for melody extraction: (1) classification approaches lose information because of the pitch categorization, and (2) there is a lack of labelled audio data for training. This project focuses on these kind of approaches and attempts to overcome these two problems using techniques that will be further discussed.

Saliency-based approaches

Almost all the salience-based approaches follow a similar procedure: first, they perform some preprocessing to the input data; then, the data is represented in the spectral domain, usually using some Fourier representation; afterwards, the salience function is computed, which is the main step of the algorithm. Finally, from the salience functions, the algorithms need to select which of the melodic contours are part of the melody, a step which is usually called tracking. In Figure 2 we display a general block diagram of salience based algorithms for melody extraction, from Salamon et al. [8]. Common preprocessing steps include filtering the input audio

Figure 2: Block diagram of salience based algorithms for melody extraction (from [8]).

signal, such in the work by Goto [9], where he defines two band-pass filters, one for the melody and another one for the bass line. Salamon and Gómez [14] use an equal loudness filter, which is motivated by human perception of frequencies; other methods include downsampling the audio or applying other band-pass filters.

Regarding the spectral representation, some authors [9][14] use STFT (short-time Fourier transform)-based methods. The former uses an STFT-based multirate filter to obtain different time-frequency resolutions: the audio is down-sampled by a decimator, which is implemented as an anti-aliasing filter with a 1/2 down-sampler.

In their implementation, the input signal is first sampled at 16kHz and is finally down-sampled to 1kHz (from 16kHz down to 1kHz through 8-4-2 kHz). The latter computes the STFT and then performs some frequency correction to overcome the low bin resolution. For this correction, they use the phase spectrum: the difference of successive phase spectra is used to compute the instantaneous frequency.

For the salience function computation, the most common method is called *harmonic summation*, where the salience of each frequency is computed as the weighted sum of the energy at each integer multiple of the spectral peaks extracted in the previous step. Goto [9], however, uses a different approach: he computes a probability density function for each of the filtered frequency components and use some statistical models to extract the fundamental frequencies using an EM algorithm. Tone models are used for this statistical approach: a tone model is the probability density function corresponding to a typical harmonic structure and it shows where the harmonics for a specific fundamental frequency typically occur. Using these tone models for all the possible fundamental frequencies and the probability density function of the extracted spectral components, the more dominant a tone model is in the mixture, the higher the probability of its fundamental frequency to be the one of the melody.

For the last step, which is the melody selection from the salience function or *tracking*, there are different methods: Goto [9] uses a salience detector using a threshold to extract the trajectories, and then multiple agents track them. Using peak closeness, exclusive allocation, and reliability of the agents, the selected melody is extracted. Clustering techniques to group melodic fragments according to some similarity measure have been used by Marolt [15]. However, both Salamon and Gómez and Paiva [14][16] apply some thresholding in order to get rid of pitch contours which do not belong to the melody. Then, in [14] they group peaks of the salience function using heuristics based on auditory streaming cues such as time or pitch continuity, which results in a set of pitch contours that are used to extract some features to select the main melody. Specifically, they filter out the non-melody contours in three steps: (1) voicing detection - determining if the melody is present by thresholding the mean salience distribution of the contour; (2) octave errors - contours which are spaced by an octave have parallel trajectories: they compare them and look at the neighbouring contours (to avoid large pitch jumps) and decide which is the correct contour. In general, the correct one also has greater salience; (3) final melody selection, which consists of selecting, from the remaining contours, which ones belong to the melody. Usually, there is only one contour left thanks to all the previous steps, but if there are several, they basically choose the one that has the highest total salience.

Source separation-based approaches

The source separation approaches aim at isolating the melody from all the other sources in the mixture. This means that if we have a polyphonic audio signal S , we can express it as follows:

$$S = S_m + S_a$$

where S_m will be the source corresponding to the melody and S_a the one corresponding to the accompaniment (note that the accompaniment in this context is everything in a signal which is not the main melody). After this assumption, we are able to use only the melodic source to extract the fundamental frequencies of the melody. In Figure 3, extracted from Salamon et al. [8], we display a block diagram with the general procedure of source separation-based algorithms.

Figure 3: Block diagram of source separation based algorithms for melody extraction (from [8]).

There are two relevant approaches to melody extraction using source separation techniques. First, the one by Durrieu et al. [17], where they model the power spectrogram of the mixture as a lead voice and an accompaniment. They make the assumption that the source of the melody will be a voice, which then allows to use a source/filter model for this part of the mixture. The source/filter model has two main parts: first, a pitched source with an f_0 parameter; then, a set of filters based on the vocal tract, in order to model the timbre of the sound (i.e. shape the vowels in human voice). The algorithm uses the expectation maximization algorithm to find the fundamental frequency of the source and the filter parameters that best fit the audio input in a frame-wise manner. The accompaniment part, also called background music, is estimated as a weighted sum of Gaussian-centered sources.

The source separation method by Tachibana et al. [18] exploits the temporal variability of melodic lines in comparison to chord sequences, which are more stable or sustained. They use a harmonic-percussive separation approach, which uses this temporal variability difference to separate percussive audio sources from other more harmonic sources. Specifically, they use the the Harmonic-Percussive Source Separation algorithm by Ono et al.[19] in two stages: first, changing the original window lengths of the algorithm, it can be used to separate sustained parts (chords, bass lines, and other accompaniment) from melodies, which are not sustained - they have more variations in time. In this first step, they get can separate chord-like sources from melodies and percussive sources, which remain together with the melody due to their temporal variability; then, in the second step they apply the original algo-

rhythm to the melodic-percussive part, in order to remove the percussion and keep (or at least enhance) the melodic line.

Data-driven approaches

Although they are not the most common, some approaches use machine learning techniques for pitch estimation. These methods need a lot of labeled data for training, and this is probably the main reason why they are not more popular. There exist some works such as the one by Ellis and Poliner [20], where they trained a support vector classifier using power spectrograms, and the resulting model was able to predict pitch labels.

Recently, deep neural networks have also been used for pitch estimation. One example is the method by Kum et al.[13], where they use multi-column deep neural networks (MCDNN) in vocal segments of music. Their MCDNN is a set of three individual deep neural networks (DNN) with the same configuration and trained using the same data, but each network has a different number of outputs. This approach, which is multi-resolution, is a first step to overcome the aforementioned problem of pitch categorization - they are able to predict pitch with three different resolutions: one semitone, half semitone, and 1/4 semitone. The network takes odd-numbered spectrogram frames as input, in order to capture contextual information. The outputs of three different DNN are combined to export a pitch estimate (using the highest resolution), and this combination is post-processed using hidden markov models (HMM). This work has two additional features:

- Data augmentation to obtain more training data. This augmentation is done by changing the global pitch of the audio. Instead of using a typical pitch-shifting method, they use a phase vocoder for a more natural pitch transposition, i.e. avoiding time stretching effects.
- Singing voice detection. The network is trained using only voiced audio frames. They use an additional DNN for the singing voice detection step, which is the previous step before pitch estimation.

Although this method is thought for vocal music excerpts, the idea behind it could be expanded to work with other kinds of music.

A second neural network approach to pitch estimation is the one presented by Verma and Schafer [21], which is intended for speech signals. It is especially interesting because they do not perform any preprocessing nor feature extraction; instead, they train a multi-layered neural network directly using audio samples. A very interesting outcome of this work, a part from its state of the art performance, is the discussion, where they analyze what the network is learning during the training stage. They look into the first layer by computing the Fourier transform of the weights of each neuron in the layer, i.e. the learned time-domain filters. This analysis shows that the first layer learns a non-linearly-spaced non-constant bandwidth (the bandwidth

depends on the center frequency of the filter) filter-bank, that spans in the range from 0 to 4000 Hz. The second interesting aspect of this approach is the fact that no pre-processing step (i.e. spectral representation, filtering or feature extraction) is required. The only requirement for the input signals is that they need to contain at least two periods. The first results they report achieve state of the art performances as compared to Salamon & Gómez [14], which is promising given that the network is trained using a speech dataset.

A similar analysis of the network is done by Sainath et al [22]. They train a CNN using raw audio for speech recognition, whereas a more typical approach is to use a mel filter bank to compute mel-spectrograms or similar audio features. Although their target is speech recognition, they perform an accurate analysis of network by looking at the weights of the filters once the training stage is finished. They found that the network learned auditory-like filterbanks where the bandwidth of the filters increases with frequency. They compute the Fourier transform of the weights of the first layer and display the center frequencies of the filters. They compare the filterbank response with a mel-like filterbank, and find that although the response is very similar, there are some differences. The main advantage of using the convolutional layer instead of using directly a filterbank is that the resulting filters are more adapted to the specific task we are working on.

Su et al. [23] present a pitch determination system for speech based on convolutional neural networks (CNN) and dynamic programming. They compute spectrogram-like features which are adapted to be more robust to noise and use a CNN to estimate the pitch candidates at each frame. The output of the network is the probability of each pitch state, where each pitch state corresponds to a specific range of real pitch values - initially, the frequencies were quantized into pitch states for classification. They convert these probabilities into a probability distribution that englobes all the real pitch values using a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM): each pitch state is modelled by a Gaussian distribution with mean the center frequency of the state and variance half of its bandwidth. Then, they select the top K pitch states (K is chosen empirically) as pitch candidates and compute the probability of the real pitch values. These probabilities are used during the dynamic programming stage to decide which is the actual pitch value at each frame of audio.

The CNN they use has two convolutional layers and two pooling layers, and the output of the second pooling layer is fed into a multi-layer perceptron with one hidden layer and an output layer with softmax activation, which is in charge of extracting the probabilities for each pitch state.

1.3 Goals and Structure of the Thesis

After reviewing the most relevant literature about choir singing voice, pitch estimation, and deep learning approaches for pitch estimation, we can confirm that very few attempts have been made to analyze choir singing recordings using deep learning. Given the aforementioned limitations of current pitch estimation algorithms to work with choral music, and the lack of annotated choir datasets, this project has

two main goals: creating new datasets to study aspects of choir singing, focusing on unison performances, and exploring deep learning architectures to estimate pitch in these recordings.

Particularly, it is focused on the creation of a dataset of unison and polyphonic performances of choral pieces in Catalan, Spanish and Latin, and the training of existing and novel neural network architectures that achieve good performances when working with choral music. In order to build new architectures we get inspiration from the work by Pons et al. [24], where they experiment with convolutional neural networks (CNN) motivated by musical aspects. They claim that using this rationale, we will be able to achieve better and more musically meaningful results.

For the unison analysis, we first perform a pitch analysis of the unison performances of the created datasets, and then train a model capable of predicting the mean pitch and its dispersion. The direct application of this is using these statistics to make synthetic choirs sound more *human* and natural. Furthermore, the pitch dispersion can also be used as a feature, e.g. to characterize different types of choir: professional vs. amateur or large vs. small ensembles.

The thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides a description of the collected material and datasets. In Chapter 3 we describe the algorithmic approaches to pitch estimation. Chapter 4 presents and discusses the results, followed by the conclusions in Chapter 5.

Chapter 2

Datasets

One of the essential parts of this project was collecting data for the analysis and experiments. As we have already mentioned, there is a lack of annotated datasets of choral music, and this has been one of the biggest challenges of the project. In this Section we present the new dataset of choir singing that was built for the project, as well as the existing datasets that were used for some of the experiments. An analysis of the new dataset is presented in Section 2.1. We recorded different choir singing performances: solo singing, unison¹, and small choir. We planned two different recordings: one with four amateur singers (soprano, alto, tenor, bass) and another one with semi-professional singers from the Anton Bruckner Choir², which is a mixed choir based in Barcelona, conducted by Júlia Sesé; they are involved in the CASAS project and take part in some of the experiments. In Figure 4 we display the picture of the choir for this year's season.

2.1 Choir Dataset

Given that we want to model unison performances, the first idea was recording a choir singing in unison. However, this approach had several drawbacks:

- If we recorded the whole choir with ambient microphones, we could not annotate the pitch of individual voices automatically because of the voice mixture. We would get an overall mean pitch, while we are interested in studying the pitch dispersion in unison performances. To this end, we needed to have each singer's pitch separately.
- To be able to automatically extract the pitch for each of the voices of the choir, we would need one microphone per singer; otherwise, everything would be mixed. This results in a lot of audio equipment, as well as problems isolating each microphone from the other ones around.

¹Unison performances are those where all the members of a choir sing the same notes (or at a distance of one octave) at the same time.

²<http://www.cdcanonbruckner.com>

Figure 4: Anton Bruckner Choir. Picture from <http://www.cdantonbruckner.com>.

- Capturing the whole choir singing in unison means that sopranos and altos would be singing the same notes, which would be one octave higher than the notes sung by tenors and basses. These octave distances would also make an accurate pitch extraction unfeasible.

Given the aforementioned limitations, we decided to record only a subset of the choir - four singers per voice (i.e. four sopranos, four altos, four tenors and four basses). With this, we are already able to model the pitch distribution in unison performances and we can record them in a more controlled environment: a recording studio. However, and according to Ternström [6], the acoustical differences between the voices affect the degree of unison: sopranos would need to sing in closer unison than basses because of the frequencies they sing and the beating phenomenon. Instead of recording 16 singers at the same time, we recorded one voice (4 singers) at a time. The organization and recording procedure are described below.

1. The CASAS project is focused on choral repertoire in Spanish, Catalan and Latin. The first step was selecting three choral pieces, one for each language. The final choice was:
 - Locus Iste, written by Anton Bruckner (Latin).
 - Niño Dios d'amor herido, written by Francisco Guerra (Spanish).
 - El Rossinyol, popular Catalan song (Catalan).

The three of them are written for a 4-voices choir, SATB³.

2. In the first recording session we recorded a quartet with one singer per voice and one microphone per singer. This data was used as reference tracks. In the

³SATB stands for Soprano-Alto-Tenor-Bass.

same session, we recorded a video of the conductor of the choir while she was conducting the three performances. This video was displayed in the following recording sessions for the singers to follow the same tempo and expression. This way, we would have all the tracks and voices synchronized for further research on multi-pitch estimation, for example. We decided to use this approach to try not to use a backing track over headphones, so that the singers could sing and interact with each other just as they would do in a live performance. However, for tuning reasons, they finally used headphones to listen to a MIDI file aligned with the conductor’s video, so they could have the tuning reference. In Figure 5 we display some pictures of the recording sessions.

(a) Recording the video of the conductor. Picture by Sonia Rodríguez.

(b) Microphone placement

(c) Three tenors singing. Picture by Cristina Calderer from Diari ARA.

Figure 5: Pictures of the recording sessions. Figure 5b is a schematic illustration of the microphone placement in the recording sessions. In the alto and tenor microphones we used an hyper-cardioid polar pattern to avoid capturing the voice from the adjacent singer. For the soprano and bass microphones we used cardioid patterns.

- Then, we did four recording sessions, one for each voice (SATB). Four singers attended each session, and we set one microphone for each one, just as in Figure 5b but the four singers sung the same part. Although we had a limited space, we placed the microphones in a way that the voice of each singer was very predominant in his/her microphone and only reached the other microphones in a residual manner. This way, the resulting audio tracks have a very

predominant voice, which allows for automatic pitch annotation using a pitch estimation algorithm for monophonic signals.

4. At the end of the recording process, for each of the three songs, we had 16 separate tracks (4 per voice) which are synchronized in time thanks to the video of the conductor. These recordings can be used both to model monophonic singing voice (isolated tracks), unison performances (mixing the four recordings of the same voice), and polyphonic performances (mixing the 16 tracks together). The main advantage of this dataset is that the same data can be used for different analysis.

Prior to the sessions that have just been described, and especially because we needed to make sure that the setting would work, we did a first recording with four amateur singers (all of them regular singers of a choir). The idea was to obtain individual recordings of a small choir (16 singers), but since we only had 4 singers, each of them sung four times. For this recording the singers had a MIDI file as a backing track, so all the recordings were time-aligned. The outcome of this preliminary recording session is a small dataset that can also be used with the same purposes: monophonic, unison and polyphonic singing analysis. For the unison modelling, which is the focus of this project, we need to mix the three tracks of the same singer as if they were sung by four different people. Although the unison performance will not be *real* in the sense that it is the same person singing three times, we can still perform an analysis of the pitch dispersion, as we show in the following Section. In this case, we only recorded a single piece, *El Rossinyol*, a Catalan popular song.

2.1.1 Preliminary Pitch Analysis of Unison Performances

Using the first recordings (amateur singers), we did an analysis of the pitch dispersion in unison performances. To do so, we extracted the fundamental frequency of each recording using the spectral autocorrelation (SAC) method, which is frequently used for pitch estimation in speech signals, and then computed the mean pitch and standard deviation over the three recordings of the same voice (SATB). Notice that this analysis is essential for the synthesis of a choir: instead of generating exact copies of one soprano to create all the sopranos, and given that we know the pitch dispersion phenomenon exists, a unison model that takes this into account would be very useful to create more human-like synthetic choirs. In Table 1 we present the tracks that were recorded in this preliminary session.

In Figure 6 we display a plot with the pitch trajectories of 12 of the 16 available voices (i.e. 3 singers per voice). We only used three tracks to obtain a clearer visualization. These pitch trajectories correspond to the first 35 seconds of *El Rossinyol*, and we used one colour per track; although in some cases two voices might intersect, in general we can clearly distinguish the four voices of the choir. However, within the same voice, we see that there are some differences in pitch and also in time. The differences in pitch, which are displayed with more detail in a zoomed version of the plot in Figure 7, are those causing the pitch dispersion, and will be

Voice	Backing track (MIDI)	Repetitions
Soprano	Yes	4
Soprano	No	2 (first half of the song)
Alto	Yes	4
Alto	No	2 (first half of the song)
Tenor	Yes	4
Tenor	No	3 (first half of the song)
Bass	Yes	4
Bass	No	2 (first half of the song)
SATB	No	1
SATB	No	1

Table 1: This table shows the preliminary recordings we did with 4 amateur singers with choir singing experience. The last column (Repetitions) means the number of times the same singer sung his/her part in order to create the unison-like effect when mixing all the tracks. The last two rows, SATB, mean that they were recorded singing as a quartet, without any backing track and interacting as they would do in a live performance.

analyzed. We do not study the differences in note onsets and offsets (time) because the synchronization between singers is not real in this case, so the time differences in the attacks, for example, might not be representative of what would happen in a real choir performance.

In Figure 8 we display some results of the initial pitch dispersion analysis. Each plot corresponds to a different voice (i.e. SATB), and it has three panes: the pitch trajectories (top), the mean pitch trajectory (middle), and the standard deviation of the pitch (bottom). It is important to point out that the standard deviation has some peaks that do not necessarily correspond to a large pitch dispersion, but to onsets and offsets which are out of synchronization. Given that the singers performed the same song four times in a row, and although they had a backing track to follow the tempo and pitch, some attacks might have a small delay compared to the other tracks. This results in an increase of the standard deviation, since we compute the statistics in a frame-wise manner.

We have previously mentioned that a model to characterize unison performances would be very useful because the pitch dispersion could be used as a feature, to distinguish different types of choir, or even which of the voices in the choir sings in unison. We did a preliminary analysis of the pitch dispersion of the recordings with the Anton Bruckner Choir to find out if it was substantially different for the different voices. The result is displayed in Figures 9 and 10, where we plotted the pitch dispersion (computed as the standard deviation of the pitch among the voices) for each part (SATB) and each piece individually, and superimposed the mean value of the dispersion for each case. To do so, we used a threshold at 15 Hz to get rid of

Figure 6: Pitch trajectories of the 12 singers performing the first 35 seconds of *El Rossinyol*. The horizontal axis is time and the vertical axis are semitones, with the reference (0.0) at 440 Hz. The aim of this scale is to see the pitch dispersion within the same voice in semitones, which are a more musical unit than Hz.

the high values that appeared in the attacks of the notes, because they are related to timing aspects which are not the focus of this particular project. By looking at the plots and especially the mean values, we see that sopranos have the highest dispersion values, followed by altos, tenors and finally basses. However, they should not be taken as absolute values because our pitch perception is logarithmic, and a 2 Hz difference in the soprano frequency range is not the same as 2 Hz in the bass range.

2.2 Monophonic Singing Voice

Besides the creation of the new dataset described in Section 2.1, we also used some existing datasets of singing voice to train and test the deep learning models. In the following subsections we briefly describe the datasets.

2.2.1 TIMIT

TIMIT is a dataset that contains sentences in English which were recorded in a clean environment - no noise. Even though it is a speech dataset, we used it to train pitch estimation models, such as in the work by Verma and Schafer [21]. This dataset

Figure 7: Zoomed version of Figure 6. This plot allows for a more accurate visualization: vibratos, displacement of notes onsets and offsets, and amount of dispersion in pitch within the same voice.

does not contain ground truth for pitch estimation, but given that the audio files do not contain noise and the speech is clear and monophonic, we used the SAC method to extract the pitch and obtain the ground truth for further supervised learning. It is important to point out that this dataset can be used to test the architectures and see how the layers perform on real data, but it would be better not to use TIMIT to train the final models. The main reason is that the frequency range of speech signals is lower than the one we use for singing, so the models are likely to fail when trying to predict higher frequencies. However, we decided to use it because of the amount of data it contains.

2.2.2 iKala

The iKala dataset [25] was developed for singing voice separation, and it contains 30-seconds excerpts of popular Chinese music performed by professional musicians and singers. The dataset contains a mono version of the songs and a stereo version, where one channel corresponds to the instrumental part and the other one to the voice. Regarding the annotations, iKala has the lyrics of the songs, as well as pitch annotations corresponding to the singing voice. These annotations are the ones we used for this project as ground truth.

Figure 8: Excerpts of the pitch dispersion analysis of the recordings explained above. The top panel of the plots shows the pitch trajectories of each of the singers of the same voice; the middle panel is the mean pitch trajectory; the bottom panel is the standard deviation of the pitch.

(a) Pitch Dispersion of the sopranos. Mean values: 2.68 Hz, 4.5 Hz and 3.34 Hz. (b) Pitch Dispersion of the altos. Mean values: 2.57 Hz, 3.87 Hz and 3.33 Hz.

Figure 9: Pitch dispersion of the sopranos and altos. The pieces are Locus Iste, Niño Dios and El Rossinyol.

(a) Pitch Dispersion of the tenors. Mean values: 1.84 Hz, 2.7 Hz and 2.27 Hz. (b) Pitch Dispersion of the basses. Mean values: 1.23 Hz, 2.53 Hz and 1.94 Hz.

Figure 10: Pitch dispersion of the tenors and basses. The pieces are Locus Iste, Niño Dios and El Rossinyol.

2.2.3 MIR-1K

Similar to iKala, this corpus contains 1000 audio excerpts of Chinese popular songs with singing voice and music accompaniment recorded separately with human-labeled pitch annotations, lyrics and also vocal/non-vocal segments [26]. The main differences between this corpus and iKala is that in this case, the singers were amateur and the audio has a lower quality.

2.2.4 Frequency Range Analysis

The first experiments for pitch estimation were done using either iKala or TIMIT. However, more data was necessary, so we decided to use both datasets together. TIMIT has a relatively small frequency range, around 100-400 Hz, which is the typical speech range, while iKala covers more or less the range between 200 and 1100 Hz, with an especially dense region between around 350 and 1000 Hz. Apparently, if we use both of them to train our models we would obtain good results in the extended frequency range between 100 and 1000 Hz. However, TIMIT has almost three times the number of examples in iKala. In Figure 11 we display the frequency histograms of TIMIT and iKala datasets, for which we first converted frequency in Hz into MIDI notes and them quantized them to $1/4$ semitone. We can see that the average number of examples in iKala is around 2000 while in TIMIT it is around 5000.

In order to overcome this, we decided to include the MIR-1K corpus, because its frequency range is similar to iKala. However, it was not enough to obtain a balanced dataset, so we finally used iKala, MIR-1K and half of the TIMIT corpus. In Figure 12 we display the individual histograms for each dataset, and the histogram of the joint dataset, where we can see that it is much more balanced for the pitch regions of interest. It is also important to mention the *unvoiced* regions of the audio signals. When we want to predict the pitch, we also want those regions where there is no singing voice to be reported as unvoiced or frequency 0. The three datasets contain a lot of unvoiced instances, many more than frames with other frequencies (although they are not shown in the previous plots for a better visualization). In order to solve this, the data is balanced just before the training stage, i.e. we check the number of

Figure 11: TIMIT and iKala pitch histograms. The former covers a larger pitch range, but contains fewer examples of each pitch; the latter covers a smaller range but has many more examples.

unvoiced frames we will use for training based on the number of voiced frames we have.

Figure 12: Pitch histograms of the three datasets individually and the joint dataset. By using only half of the TIMIT dataset we obtain a much more balanced corpus. Notice that getting a flat histogram, i.e. same number of examples for each pitch, would require a very accurate and costly analysis of all the labels for each dataset.

Chapter 3

Selected Approaches

This Chapter presents the main tasks of the project: first, in Section 3.1, the data preprocessing stage, where we prepare the data for further analysis; then, the neural networks that were implemented are described in Section 3.2; finally, in Section 3.3 we present the process we followed for the pitch analysis of unison performances.

3.1 Data Preprocessing

In Chapter 2 we presented all the data that was collected and recorded for this project. Given that we perform several analysis (which are described in Sections 3.2 and 3.3), we worked with different types of data. Our neural networks basically use two types of input: raw audio (i.e. audio samples directly from the waveform) and constant-Q transform (CQT), which are spectrogram-like features that will be described below.

The main idea behind using raw audio instead of computing audio features is that deep learning architectures should be capable of computing new audio features that will probably be more suitable to reach the desired target, because the networks are expected to compute more *specialized* representations. Especially in the field of speech recognition, researchers train their neural networks directly with frames of audio samples, and in some cases, the data does not even require any preprocessing nor postprocessing.

On the other hand, there are some well-known audio features which are already used for particular tasks that allow for good performances. For example, MFCCs are used for speech-related tasks, and they are good enough for most applications. The constant-Q transform, which is used in this project, is a transformation similar to the Fourier transform. According to Blankertz [27], the constant-Q transform uses a bank of filters with geometrically spaced center frequencies given by:

$$f_k = f_0 \cdot 2^{\frac{k}{b}}, k = 0, \dots$$

where b is the number of filters per octave. The main property of this transform is that the ratio of frequency to resolution (Q) is constant; another important feature is that it increases the time resolution in high frequencies, just as the human auditory system does. This is why these features might be useful for extracting the pitch. In Figure 13 we display an example of the CQT of an audio signal where we can clearly see the melody that the singer is producing. We compute the CQT using Librosa, a Python library for audio and music signal analysis developed by McFee et al. [28].

Figure 13: Example of the CQT computed on a singing voice recording from iKala.

3.1.1 Raw Audio

When working with audio samples, we can not use the whole audio recording, but we need to divide it into chunks. It is critical to choose the optimal length to slice the audio: if we take too small segments, we might not be able to extract the pitch in low frequencies, because we might be taking less than one period or two; on the contrary, if we use slices which are too large, we might take more than one pitch inside the same window, which would also result in confusion. According to Verma and Schafer [21], we need at least two periods of the signal to be able to predict the pitch accurately, but larger segments might lead to errors, so we need a compromise.

We will work with a pitch range between 40 Hz and around 1000 Hz, although it is larger than the expected vocal range, we decided to use a broader interval just in case. If the lowest frequency is 40 Hz, we compute the length of two periods as follows:

$$f_{min} = 40 \text{ Hz}$$

$$T_{min} = \frac{1}{f} = \frac{1}{40} = 0.025 \text{ sec}$$

The largest period will be 0.025 seconds, and we use twice this period as our frame length. Given that we work with audio sampled at 44100 Hz (f_s) to avoid losing information:

$$L = 2 \cdot T_{min} = 0.05 \text{ sec}$$

which is very close to the 60 ms Verma and Schafer use in their paper [21]. In samples, we compute the length as:

$$L_{samples} = L f_s = 0.05 \cdot 44100 = 2205 \text{ samples}$$

To train our deep learning models with audio samples, we segment the audio in groups of 2205 samples. In order not to miss any potential information, we overlapped the segments, and used a hop size of 10 ms. This means that the pitch predictions will have a resolution of 10 ms, i.e. every 10 ms we will have a pitch estimate.

3.1.2 Constant-Q Transform

Several MIR tasks that use neural networks, such as music genre or instrument classification, use the spectrogram of the audio as input. Others, such as speech recognition, use MFCCs (Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients). As we have already mentioned, we will use the constant-Q transform, which is a more suitable representation for pitch estimation, and it can also be treated as an image, just as the spectrogram. We follow the strategy by Kum et al. [13] and apply it to the CQT instead of using their log-spectrograms. We use a hop length of 10 ms (just as in the case of raw audio) and compute the CQT with minimum frequency 40 Hz, 100 CQ-bins and 24 bins per octave. Then, these CQT features are rearranged as shown in Figure 14: we slice the CQT output into groups of 5 frames, which will be the inputs to our system. Given that each frame is computed at every 10 ms, the resulting groups will be 50 ms long, also as in the raw audio case.

3.1.3 Pitch Labels

The iKala and MIR-1K datasets contain pitch labels as ground truth for pitch estimation. TIMIT does not, but as has been already mentioned, we used the SAC method to obtain them. Throughout the project we worked with two different modalities of the pitch labels: continuous values of pitch in Hertz and discrete values as MIDI numbers. We needed the information in these two formats for different approaches to pitch estimation: different activations in the last layer of the deep learning architectures require different ground truth formats.

To use the frequency values in Hz we do not need to process the labels. We only need to have one pitch value per frame of analysis: we have one value every 10 ms. In the case of CQT, for each data slice we assign the pitch label of the frame in the middle, i.e. the third one.

Figure 14: Arrangement of the CQT data for analysis. Each set of 5 frames is obtained by moving one frame forward at a time and keeping the current and the following four frames.

The discrete values are obtained using the formula from Kum et al. [13]:

$$s = \lceil res \cdot (69 + 12 \cdot \log_2(\frac{f}{440})) \rceil / res$$

where res is the desired resolution of the pitch (i.e. $res = 1$ means 1 semitone resolution, $res = 2$ is half semitone resolution and $res = 4$ is 1/4 semitone resolution) and f is the frequency in Hz. The result s will be the quantized pitch with the given resolution. We basically used half semitone resolution, provided that 1/4 semitone was too much for our networks, as will be further discussed.

3.2 Deep Learning Architectures for Pitch Estimation

This section will describe the deep learning architectures that have been trained to estimate pitch in monophonic singing voice. We basically used two types of neural networks: fully connected (following the examples in [13] and [21]) and convolutional as in [23]. In the following subsections we describe the specific networks that have been used in the project.

3.2.1 Fully Connected Neural Networks

Fully connected neural networks (FCNN) are one of the most basic types of neural networks. In a FCNN, every single neuron in a layer is connected to all the neurons in the previous layer, as in Figure 15. Taking advantage of this, the activations of the neurons are computed by a matrix multiplication plus a bias.

We built the multi-layer network presented by Verma and Schafer in [21] to train it with audio samples (see Section 3.1 for more details). This network has three hidden layers, each one with 2048 units and 50% dropout; all layers have a ReLU activation except for the output layer, which has as many units as pitch candidates and softmax activation, which outputs the probabilities for each state.

Figure 15: Scheme of the fully-connected neural network by Verma and Schafer [21].

3.2.2 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) were first thought for images and computer vision applications, and they are based on the same idea that neurons receive inputs, perform some operations and produce outputs accordingly. There are three basic types of layers that are often used in CNNs: convolutional, pooling and fully connected layers. In the convolutional layers, there is a set of filters and each one is convolved with the input. This convolution produces a 2-dimensional activation map at the output. During the training stage, the network learns filters that respond to specific patterns or shapes, such as edges or colour.

Although this kind of networks are widely used with images, researchers started using them for audio and music related applications. In such cases, the input is a spectrogram (or a similar 2D representation of the audio), which is, in fact, an image-like representation of an audio signal. They are usually used for MIR tasks such as music genre classification or instrument detection. However, and following the approach by Kum et al. [13], we decided to use a CNN for pitch estimation using three different CNN architectures: one using raw audio as input (1) and a two different ones using constant-Q transform (2) and (3).

The first network (1) uses chunks of audio samples in the input layer, followed

by two convolutional layers with 32 and 64 filters respectively. After these two layers there are two fully-connected layers with 2048 and 512 neurons each, which are in charge of the classification process itself, i.e. using the specialized features generated by the convolutional layers to assign one pitch state to each input chunk. The output layer contains as many neurons as possible pitch states, and uses softmax activation. In Figure 16 we display the scheme of this network. This is the typi-

Figure 16: Scheme of the convolutional neural network used with audio samples. The horizontal blocks on the left correspond to audio chunks and the darker rectangles inside represent the convolutions. The two vertical blocks in the middle are the fully-connected layers, which consist of neurons connected with each other. The last vertical block is the output layer with softmax.

cal activation function used in classification procedures, which basically consists of computing the probability of the input to belong to each of the potential classes. In this case we have so many classes because each pitch state is translated into a class. When using softmax, it is necessary to use a specific number of pitch states, which means using quantized pitch values. When we quantize the pitch using the method described by Kum et al. [13], we define the pitch resolution we will work with. First, we work with half semitone resolution, which is enough for pitch estimation applications. However, as we will see later, this resolution might not be enough for the unison analysis we need to do.

The second network (2) is displayed in Figure 17 and has many differences as compared to (1). First, the input data is different: in this case we are using CQT data, which are, in fact, images. Instead of using the CQT of the whole audio signal, we use small chunks of it, which results in input images of size 100×5 . This way, we will estimate the pitch for each of these chunks.

The network itself has two convolutional layers: the first one with 64 filters and the second one with twice as this, 128. The filter shapes are $(10, 1)$ and $(5, 1)$ respectively, aiming to capture different information. However, and following the work by Pons et al. [24], we use vertical filters because we are interested in the frequency axis

information. The filter shapes were defined empirically, and each layer has ReLU activation. These two convolutional layers are followed by one fully-connected layer with 100 units and the output layer with as many units as pitch classes - 103 in most cases. The third network (3) is displayed in Figure 18 and is similar to the previous

Figure 17: Scheme of the first convolutional neural network used with CQT data. The big light grey rectangles correspond to the CQT chunks, and the small vertical dark grey blocks are the convolutions. Similar to the previous network, the vertical block in the right side is the fully-connected layer, which consist of neurons connected with each other. The last vertical block is the output layer with softmax.

one, network (2). It is also a CNN and it uses the same data - CQT. However, we wanted to try a more complex network to see if it improved the performance. We decided to build a deeper network - with more layers.

In this case, the network has four convolutional layers: the first one with 128 filters and the others with 64. The filter shapes vary between layers aiming to capture different information. The filter shapes are defined empirically and are $(5, 1), (3, 1), (3, 1), (30, 1)$, also using the approach by Pons et al. [24]. Each of these convolutional layers has ReLU activation, and in this case, they are followed by two fully-connected layers, just as in (1). These layers contain 1024 and 512 neurons respectively, and the output layer is the same as before, with as many neurons as pitch states and softmax activation. These three networks use softmax activation in the last layer. Typical classification tasks in MIR are music genre or mood classification, which might have 8-10 possible classes. However, in the case of pitch estimation, every pitch class in our dataset represents a different class at the output. In order to define the pitch classes, we need to set the minimum and maximum frequency values and we also need to define the frequency resolution we want to work with. We tried one, half and $1/4$ of semitone as resolutions, and as we expected, the accuracy of the models decreases when we increase the resolution. One semitone is a very low pitch resolution for most applications, so we decided to go for half and quarter. However, with half semitone, and using a frequency range more or less between 40 and 900 Hz, we already had 102 pitch classes plus the unvoiced class, which were

Figure 18: Scheme of the deep convolutional neural network used with CQT data. Just as in Figure 17, the big light grey rectangles correspond to the CQT chunks, and the small vertical dark grey blocks are the convolutions. The last layers are fully-connected.

a lot for the data we had. Doubling the resolution means doubling the number of classes, which results in very low accuracies because we do not have enough data to perform such a big classification task.

The solution we propose to overcome this issue is changing the activation function in the last layer to transform the classification problem into a regression-like problem. Instead of using discrete values at the output, we want to predict continuous pitch values. To this end, we use a rectifier function as activation, which computes a single output value at each frame instead of computing all the probabilities. This allows to predict any pitch value, without the need to specify either the frequency range nor the pitch resolution. Additionally, to perform the unison analysis of the choir performances (see Section 3.3), half semitone resolution is not enough: if we work with discrete values, when we compute the standard deviation of the pitch values across the four singers of the same voice (e.g. alto), we get either 0 or a very low value, because the pitch dispersion might be smaller than the resolution of the networks, i.e. two pitch values that are closer together than one semitone will become the same number in our pitch discretization, and this is not useful for the unison analysis.

Using the network that obtains better performance, we change the last layer activation so that it computes a single pitch value.

3.3 Choir Unison Performances Modelling

In this Section we talk about how to model a unison performance of a choir. When all the singers of a choir sing the same note, listeners perceive one single pitch; however, when we dig into the actual frequencies that are produced by each of them, we discover that the pitch the audience perceives is a mix of very similar but not exact copies of the perceived pitch. This is a very important aspect of choir singing, and it helps shaping the overall timbre of a choir. In choir singing synthesis, which is a part of the CASAS project, it is very important to take this aspect into account, otherwise the synthesis would not sound natural: if a synthetic choir singing in unison is built by adding together copies of the same singer, it would not sound as an actual choir. In order to achieve this effect, we need to use actual unison performances and model them to use this information for further synthesis.

A unison performance can be modelled with two parameters: the mean pitch and the standard deviation - or pitch dispersion. We want to build a model capable of extracting this information from a recording of a unison performance. To do so, we decided to train a neural network based on the ones we used for the monophonic pitch estimation and adapt it to predict these two values. However, we first need to prepare the available data to train this new model.

The main idea is to use the models for monophonic signals to predict the pitch in the individual recordings of the choir dataset (see Section 2.1). Thanks to the microphone placement, in general we have a very predominant voice in each microphone, so we can extract the pitch of each voice individually. Then, using the pitch labels predicted by the model, we compute the mean and the standard deviation at each frame of the audio. For each piece, we have the typical SATB setting, and for each of these voices we have four singers; we compute the mean and deviation of these four singers for each part. With these steps we obtain the labels that will be used as targets to train the model. The data is obtained by mixing the recordings of the four singers per voice together, creating the unison.

To illustrate this, in Figure 19 we display an example of the data we work with: in the top panel of the figure we see the pitch trajectories of four singers (basses), and the middle and bottom panel show the mean pitch and the standard deviation respectively. It is important to point out that the highest peaks of the standard deviation are likely to represent timing differences in the attacks of the notes, which are not the focus of this work. A second example is shown in Figure 20, which is a very short excerpt of the soprano part of the same piece. It allows to clearly see the pitch dispersion in a stable note. The three panels of the plot are the same as in Figure 19.

We also want to illustrate the behaviour of the pitch dispersion when we add more singers, e.g. the difference between having 2 singers or 4, which is the maximum for our dataset. We used the ground truth pitch labels for each individual voice to compute the dispersion (i.e. the standard deviation) for each voice (SATB) when there are 2, 3 and 4 people singing in unison. Intuitively, we would expect an

Figure 19: This is a short excerpt of the bass part of *El Rossinyol*, the Catalan song of the repertoire. Each of the trajectories in the top pane corresponds to one singer. Since they are four basses, they sing the same, i.e. unison, but we can see that there are some slight differences in pitch, which cause the pitch dispersion (standard deviation) shown in the bottom panel. In the middle we see the mean pitch trajectory, which is easily obtained by computing the mean of the four voices at each frame.

Figure 20: This is a short excerpt of the soprano part of *El Rossinyol*, the Catalan song of the repertoire. It corresponds to a single note sung by four sopranos. The y-axis shows a semitone scale (with the 0 reference at 440 Hz), and in the top panel we see that, at some points, the pitch trajectories differ up to more than half semitone.

		2 singers	3 singers	4 singers
Locus Iste	Alto	1.5	2.1	2.6
	Soprano	1.8	2.3	2.7
	Tenor	1.3	1.7	1.8
	Bass	0.8	1.1	1.2
Niño Dios	Alto	2.5	3.4	3.9
	Soprano	3.2	4.1	4.5
	Tenor	1.9	2.5	2.8
	Bass	1.8	2.3	2.5
El Rossinyol	Alto	2	2.8	3.3
	Soprano	2.47	3	3.3
	Tenor	1.6	2.1	2.2
	Bass	1.3	1.8	2

Table 2: Evolution of the pitch dispersion when adding more singers to the unison performance. The values are in Hz.

increase of the pitch dispersion when adding more singers, and it is, in fact, what happens in our dataset, as we can observe in Table 2: the more singers, we larger the dispersion. This confirms our hypothesis that the dispersion could be used as a feature to distinguish small choirs from bigger ones.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the experiments carried out during the project, together with their corresponding results and evaluation. We first describe the methodology that has been used to evaluate the performance of the algorithms, and then we present all the results. We start with the monophonic pitch estimation part, which is followed by the unison modelling results.

4.1 Evaluation Strategies

To evaluate the performance of the models we used a method that consists of two steps. The first one is checking the behaviour of the model using a synthetic linear chirp signal; the second step is using the evaluation metrics for audio melody extraction from MIREX ¹ to compare the pitch predictions against the ground truth pitch labels.

4.1.1 Model Behaviour

A linear chirp signal is a signal that increases (or decreases) its frequency in time in a linear manner. Following the approach by Verma and Schafer [21], we use this signal as input to our models and predict the pitch labels. We created the chirp using the software Audacity, and it covers the frequency range between 30 Hz and 1000 Hz. In order to see if the models are able to predict unvoiced segments, we inserted two silence regions in the signal. The spectrogram of the signal is displayed in Figure 21.

4.1.2 Evaluation Metrics

For the quantitative evaluation of the models, we use them to predict the pitch and then compare these predictions with the ground truth, i.e. the real pitch labels. As

¹MIREX (Music Information Retrieval Evaluation eXchange) is an annual competition of MIR tasks, including audio melody extraction (http://www.music-ir.org/mirex/wiki/2016:Audio_Melody_Extraction).

Figure 21: Linear chirp signal covering the frequency range 30-1000 Hz. Two regions of silence were inserted in the middle of the signal to obtain more information about the models.

we have mentioned before, we used the evaluation metrics established in MIREX (descriptions based on Bosch et al.[29]):

- Voicing recall (VR): percentage of frames labelled as voiced in the ground truth that are estimated as voiced by the algorithm.
- Voicing false alarm (VFA): percentage of frames labelled as unvoiced in the ground truth that are mistakenly estimated as voiced by the algorithm.
- Raw pitch accuracy (RPA): percentage of voiced frames in the ground truth for which the prediction is correct within $1/4$ of semitone.
- Raw chroma accuracy (RCA): measure of pitch accuracy in which both estimated and ground truth pitches are mapped into one octave, ignoring the octave errors.
- Overall accuracy (OA): percentage of frames that were correctly labelled both in terms of the voicing and the pitch.

These metrics are computed using the Python library `mir_eval` [30].

4.2 Chirp Signal Results

In Figure 22 we display the response of the four main models to the chirp signal mentioned above. In the top pane of the plots we see the activation map at the output of the networks, because these four models have softmax activation in the last layer. These maps show the probability of each pitch class (y -axis) to be the one at each frame (x -axis). The lighter the colour, the higher the probability. Similarly, the bottom pane displays the predicted pitch labels - the pitch class with maximum probability. Since our chirp signal increases its frequency linearly in time, we expect

Figure 22: Response of the models to a chirp signal. All subfigures contain two panels: the one on the top is the activation map at the output of the network and the bottom one shows the predicted labels.

the labels to draw a straight line with a positive slope. As mentioned above, this signal covers the frequency range from 30 Hz to 1000 Hz, so we would expect the pitch labels to cover this range too. However, looking at the plots we can see some issues: first, there are some regions with a lot of confusion, especially in the two models on the top; then, we also see that the pitch predictions do not start at the beginning of the audio (frequency 30 Hz) and they do not last until the end of the file (frequency 1000 Hz) either. This happens because the models are not capable of predicting frequencies in these low and high frequency ranges: if we go back to Section 2.2 we see that the datasets used to train the models do not contain any (or very few) instances with frequencies in these ranges. This makes the models report either frequency 0 or any other random number in these ranges, because during they have not been optimized to predict these values during the training stage. If we analyze these responses we also notice that the results are apparently better with constant-Q data (22d and 22c) than with raw audio samples (22a and 22b).

- The first model (22a) is the architecture by Verma and Schafer [21], and it was trained with the three datasets (iKala, MIR-1K and TIMIT). We see that

the silences are perfectly predicted as frequency 0, and the range between 100 Hz and 500 Hz (approximately) also works fine. However, after 500 Hz, the network starts predicting lower pitches, which correspond to the lower octave of the actual frequencies. This happens because although the model does not have information about higher pitches, it detects some kind of sub-harmonic structure in the signal that results in predicting the labels of the octave just below. This result already suggests that this model might have octave errors².

- The second model (22b) is the one in Figure 16, which was also trained with the three datasets. We find a pattern similar to the one in the previous case; however, the correct predictions do not reach 500 Hz, so the working frequency range is smaller than 22a.
- The third model (22c) is the one in Figure 17 and we already see that it works better than the previous two: it has less errors at the boundaries (i.e. it directly predicts the regions as unvoiced instead of assigning other wrong values), and the frequency range where it works is a little bit wider because it predicts some frequencies higher than 500 Hz.
- The last model (22d) is the one in Figure 18, a network which is deeper (has more layers) than the other ones. Looking at the two plots, we see that it is capable of predicting pitch up to 600 Hz, which is more than the previous models. It is also more stable, because it does not have wrong numbers in the middle of the *working range*. There is one reason why this model works with higher frequencies: it was trained using the three datasets plus some data of the recordings we did with the Anton Bruckner Choir. The alto and soprano parts have some higher frequencies, and this broadens the pitch range a little bit.

Until now, the models we have seen use softmax activation in the last layer, which means that the pitch needs to be categorized. As we have mentioned at the end of Section 3.2, we also trained one network to predict continuous pitch values instead of discrete. To do so, we used the model with better performance (the one in Figure 22d, as will be shown below) and changed the last layer. In this case, we do not obtain an activation map at the output, but the pitch labels directly. The response of this model to the same chirp signal is displayed in Figure 23, where we see the frequency values. In this case the pitch labels almost reach 600 Hz, which is a little bit less than what we obtained with the same model but using softmax. However, even though this model has a slightly narrower pitch range, it can predict continuous values, which are more suitable for applications where more precision in the pitch values is necessary, e.g. the analysis of tuning.

²An octave error in pitch estimation is predicting the frequency in the octave below (or above) the actual pitch.

Figure 23: Pitch labels predicted by the model in Figure 18 with rectify activation in the last layer when the input is the chirp signal described above.

4.3 Quantitative Evaluation

This section presents the evaluation of the models using the metrics described at the beginning of the chapter. This quantitative evaluation was carried out using the Python library `mir_eval` [30] and using the three datasets (iKala, MIR-1K and TIMIT) as well as the choir dataset that was created for the project. We divide the section into several parts, one per model. For each model, we present the metrics averaged along each of the datasets separately. For the choir dataset, we also split the results between different voices because it gives a better understanding of what the models are doing.

It is important to mention that all the models were evaluated using the pitch values in Hz: the predictions made by the models that quantize the pitch (those with softmax activation) were converted into Hz to compare them with the original pitch labels. The continuous pitch values were taken directly from the model, as they are already in Hz. Remember that the pitch accuracy metric has a tolerance of $1/4$ semitone.

4.3.1 Fully Connected Neural Network with raw audio

This model, which is based on the architecture by Verma and Schafer [21], was trained with the three datasets of the project. In this case we did not include the choir dataset because the process of recording was long and the data was not available. In Table 3 we display the results of the evaluation. There are two aspects that we want to emphasize about the results in Table 3: first, the high values of the voicing false alarm (VFA). We want this metric to have the lowest possible value; otherwise, it means that we are reporting pitch labels for unvoiced frames. Second, we also want to highlight the results for the soprano of the choir dataset: while the raw pitch accuracy is low (68.1%) the raw chroma accuracy is more than 90%. This confirms the octave errors suggested before for Figure 22a. Taking this into account, we would conclude that this model has some limitations in the voicing detection and octave errors with high frequencies. We hypothesize that this could be solved by

DATASET	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
iKala	98.6	56.8	70.9	71.8	64.9
MIR-1K	99.2	48.3	86.1	88.2	76.9
TIMIT	97.2	48.6	39.9	60.3	45.4
Choir: Soprano	99.8	22.4	68.4	91.9	71.6
Choir: Alto	99.9	30.8	93.5	93.9	88.8
Choir: Tenor	99.6	26.7	91.3	92.2	87.6
Choir: Bass	99.5	29.3	52.5	56.7	60.3

Table 3: Pitch estimation results with the fully-connected network in Figure 15. The best accuracies are highlighted in bold.

increasing the amount of training instances in this frequency range. Notice that the best performance is with alto and tenor voices, which are in a mid-frequency range that corresponds to the pitch distribution of the training datasets.

4.3.2 Convolutional Neural Network with raw audio

The network we presented in Figure 16 uses raw audio chunks as input and the results we obtained are in Table 4. We see that the pitch and chroma accuracies are low, except for the tenors. It is important to mention that voicing detection does not work as expected, just as in the previous case. Since both networks use audio samples as input, we hypothesize that with this type of data it is more difficult to report whether an audio segment is voiced or unvoiced. These voicing detection results differ a lot from the ones with constant-Q, as we will see in the next sections. These results show evidence that this architecture is not the right one to predict pitch. They might also suggest that the data is not treated properly: we are using audio segments with a specific size, 50 ms, a choice that was inspired by Verma and Schafer [21]; however, they were using a fully-connected network, the one in 15, and maybe this size is no longer suitable for convolutions. We would need to find the compromise between changing the size of the audio chunks and adding more layers to the network. The shape of the convolutional filters is also crucial in this case: we might be losing important information if it is not an optimal shape. More experiments will be carried out to improve the performance of this model, because we are very interested in obtaining a CNN that directly uses audio samples.

4.3.3 Convolutional Neural Network with CQT

Table 5 shows the evaluation results with the CNN with softmax activation that has two convolutional layers and uses constant-Q data as input. It was also trained with the three datasets (see Section 2.2).

In this case, we do not see abrupt changes between RPA and RCA, which suggests that octave errors are not a big issue with this model. The VFA has decreased a lot in comparison with the previous model (Table 3), which means that the voicing

DATASET	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
iKala	97.5	41.4	51	51	55.1
MIR-1K	98.6	31.9	57.5	57.6	61.5
TIMIT	95.2	26.5	37.4	38.6	54.6
Choir: Soprano	88.9	1.9	15.3	15.4	40.2
Choir: Alto	99.7	9.6	54.7	54.7	64.2
Choir: Tenor	98.8	3.5	78.5	78.5	83.5
Choir: Bass	99.3	12.9	33.3	33.4	49.9

Table 4: Pitch estimation results with the CNN network in Figure 16. The best accuracies are highlighted in bold.

DATASET	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
iKala	92.9	12.4	82.2	82.8	84.6
MIR-1K	96	9.1	86	86.5	87.8
TIMIT	89.6	19.1	68.4	71	74.4
Choir: Soprano	84.8	1	81.3	82.4	86
Choir: Alto	98.9	5.6	93.4	93.5	93.6
Choir: Tenor	96.5	3.2	89.7	90	91.2
Choir: Bass	92.9	2.8	58.2	58.7	70.8

Table 5: Pitch estimation results with the convolutional neural network using constant-Q in Figure 17. The best accuracies are highlighted in bold.

detection works much better with this model.

4.3.4 Deep Convolutional Neural Network with CQT

After trying the CNN with CQT presented above (Table 5), we decided to try adding more layers to the network, so we built the network in Figure 18. Although we already had fairly good results with the CNN with two convolutional layers, it had poor results in some cases (TIMIT, bass), so we trained a deeper network to see if we could improve the performance. In this case, and given that we already had the choir dataset ready, we added this data to train the network and the results are presented in Table 6. We observe that the accuracies for TIMIT increase with respect to the previous network (see Table 5 for comparison); we also improve the results regarding voicing detection, given that the false alarm rate decreases in all the cases. However, if we focus in the choir dataset, we observe that the model performance is similar in all the voices except the soprano, where the performance is lower than with the previous model. Looking at the overall accuracy (OA), it increases for iKala, MIR-1K and TIMIT, while it remains almost the same for alto, tenor and bass.

DATASET	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
iKala	95	5.8	87.5	88	90.3
MIR-1K	96.2	4.9	89.2	89.6	91.1
TIMIT	92.6	6.6	81.5	82	87.2
Choir: Soprano	70.7	2.1	67.4	71.6	75.8
Choir: Alto	98.1	4.3	93	93.1	93.5
Choir: Tenor	94.5	1.4	88.5	88.8	90.6
Choir: Bass	90.1	1.7	57.6	58	70.6

Table 6: Pitch estimation results with the deep convolutional neural network using constant-Q in Figure 18. The best accuracies are highlighted in bold.

DATASET	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
iKala	97.6	13.8	63	63.5	71.7
MIR-1K	98.5	12.1	51.4	52	62.6
TIMIT	97.2	18.5	18.7	19.6	48.3
Choir: Soprano	78.8	6.8	21.2	25.2	39.7
Choir: Alto	99.3	9.8	81.8	82	83.6
Choir: Tenor	96.7	3.9	41	41.5	53.1
Choir: Bass	95.7	3.5	11.8	12.9	33.5

Table 7: Pitch estimation results with the deep convolutional neural network for continuous values using constant-Q. The best accuracies are highlighted in bold.

4.3.5 Deep Convolutional Neural Network with CQT and rectifier function

The last architecture we present in this section is the deep CNN with CQT with a different output layer. As mentioned throughout this text, we need more pitch resolution than half semitone for the unison modelling, so we took this architecture because it was the one with the best overall performance and changed the output layer so that it is capable of predicting continuous pitch values. Instead of having many units, the last layer will have only one unit and a rectifier activation function. This function combines the outputs of the previous layer and computes a single value that will be the output of the network.

This network was trained with all the data (3 datasets + choir dataset), but instead of quantizing the pitch values, we use the original pitch values in Hz. The results are presented in Table 7, where we can see that they are worse than the ones from previous models. This model needs to be improved, and probably using more data would help to improve its performance. From the numbers in Table 7 we see that this model needs to improve, especially in the low (bass) and high (soprano) frequency ranges. Although for the alto parts we have a good performance, the results

DATASET	RPA (%)	RCA (%)
iKala	81.6	83.1
MIR-1K	87.4	88.5
TIMIT	77.1	82.7
Soprano	97.1	97.4
Alto	96.2	96.6
Tenor	94.9	95.4
Bass	61.8	63.3

Table 8: Pitch prediction results using YIN [11].

for the monophonic signals are much worse than with the other models. Especially the TIMIT dataset, which has lower frequencies because it consists of speech signals, has very low accuracies. These errors might have different sources: lack of data for training, especially in the frequency boundaries; changing the activation in the last layer might require more training data or more iterations, or maybe the fact that the dataset was not completely balanced has much more impact in this case than in a classification problem (such as the other models).

4.3.6 Comparison with state-of-the-art

In order to provide a reference of performance, we run the YIN [11] algorithm with our dataset and report the results in Table 8. Note that this algorithm does not perform any voicing detection; therefore, the voicing detection false alarm rate and overall accuracy do not make sense in this case, so we do not display them. By looking at Table 8 we see that in most of the cases, the YIN algorithm obtains higher accuracies than our models. However, there are some exceptions: in Table 6 we report 89.9% of RPA for the MIR-1K dataset, while YIN obtains 87%. We also outperform YIN with the iKala dataset. Additionally, we find some similarities between these results and ours: for the basses we see a drop of the performance, probably because of the very low frequencies that appear in the recordings; we also obtain lower accuracies with the TIMIT dataset. In this case, however, the best result for the choir are the sopranos, while in our models, the best was always the alto voice.

Finally, to get an overview of all the results, in Table 9 we find the results averaged for all the data. The best values for each metric are highlighted in bold, and the results using YIN are also displayed for comparison purposes.

4.4 Choir Unison Modelling Results

In Section 3.3 we explained how we can model unison performances: using a mean pitch and a dispersion (or standard deviation). We built a model based on the deep CNN with CQT in Figure 18 that given an audio recording, it computes the mean

Model	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)
CNN CQ	93.1	7.6	79.9	80.7	84.1
FCNN	99.1	37.6	71.8	79.3	70.8
CNN raw	96.9	18.2	46.8	47	58.4
Deep CNN CQ	91	3.8	80.7	81.6	85.6
Deep CNNCQ rectify	94.8	9.8	41.3	42.4	56.1
YIN			85.2	86.7	

Table 9: Overview of the results.

pitch and standard deviation, both of them in Hz. It is very important to mention that this model was trained with very few data: the only data available for this task was the choir dataset, which contains 13 audio recordings - three pieces with four voices each plus an additional tenor voice that was recorded additionally. This is a very small dataset to train a model, and this is why we are probably overfitting. However, as this is a very novel method for modelling unison performances, it was interesting to see how the model worked, even with overfitting.

For this, the network we used is the same as in Section 4.3.5 but instead of having one single unit in the output layer, we have two units: one for the mean and a second one for the standard deviation. Since the model we trained to predict continuous pitch values has yet to be improved, we decided to create the ground truth for this unison model with the SAC method, which has already been mentioned. However, once we have a model that reaches state-of-the-art performances, we will change the method and use our own architecture.

At the output of the unison model we obtain two values, which have to be evaluated separately. We decided to use the same method (the `mir_eval` library) for the mean pitch, because it is frequency just as in the other cases; however, for the standard deviation this method was not giving an actual view of the performance. After some trials with different methods and also trying different tolerance values, we decided to evaluate the standard deviation value with a tolerance of 3 Hz and computing only the accuracy value. In Table 10 we display the results of the unison model; we observe that the results for the mean more or less follow the same pattern as the other pitch estimation models: the best performances are obtained with altos, then soprano or tenor and finally, bass. However, these results might be biased because of the potential overfitting of the network. Regarding the standard deviation, the accuracies are different, because the basses obtain higher values than the rest. More data and a deeper analysis of the results would be necessary to address this problem, and it will be further studied during the development of the CASAS project.

Voice	VR (%)	VFA (%)	RPA (%)	RCA (%)	OA (%)	Dispersion accuracy (%)
Soprano	99.9	9	77.2	77.5	81.7	48.5
Alto	99.8	1.6	86.3	86.6	88.4	51.7
Tenor	99.5	2.4	67.8	68	73.2	67.9
Bass	99	3.1	48.2	48.6	61.4	70.5

Table 10: Results of the unison model: columns 2 to 6 correspond to the mean pitch and the last one to the dispersion. The MIREX evaluation metrics are used for the mean pitch, while the procedure described above is used to evaluate the dispersion.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future Work

The first goal of this project was the creation of a new dataset of choir singing in an attempt to overcome the lack of annotated data we have for choir-related applications. As part of the CASAS project, we have been able to carry out the recording sessions that have been described above with the singers of the Anton Bruckner Choir, obtaining very relevant data for the research community that will be published soon. However, and although this choir dataset is a great contribution, we would still need more data for a complete analysis of choir singing, especially for unison and polyphonic performances: the models for the monophonic pitch estimation can be trained with standard monophonic singing signals, which are already available (iKala, MIR-1K, TIMIT and other datasets). However, and taking into account that a choir is not a set of exact copies of a singer, to model the pitch of a choir we need much more precision, which requires a lot of data if we work with data-driven approaches. This dataset is the first step of the work that still needs to be done in choir singing analysis.

Our second goal was to research on data-driven methods for pitch estimation, and we found that although there are some approaches that use either machine or deep learning algorithms to estimate the pitch of audio signals, it is not the most common approach, mostly because of the lack of annotated data. Most of the approaches that use neural networks for MIR tasks work with spectrograms as input data, and we tried two different types of data: raw audio and constant-Q transform. Although our results with raw audio can still improve, we built an end-to-end model that does not need any pre-processing or feature extraction; furthermore, we also decided to use constant-Q instead of spectrograms because it is a more suitable representation of the audio for applications related to the pitch. The results with CQT confirm that it is, indeed, a good audio representation for pitch estimation.

After all the experiments and their corresponding evaluations, we can confirm that some of our models, especially the ones that use constant-Q transform as input, achieve state-of-the-art performances and in some cases even surpass them. However, from the results we detected that the training was not uniform along the frequencies: while for the mid-frequencies the accuracies are high, for low frequencies

(approximately below 150 Hz) and high frequencies (above 650 Hz more or less), the models show a drop in their performance. Even though the datasets contain instances of all the frequencies in the defined frequency range, they seem not to be balanced enough to work well with all the pitch range. However, we managed to solve a problem we encountered during the development of the project: before we balanced the dataset, we had a lot of unvoiced instances, which resulted in models biased towards unvoiced frames. This means that while they were capable of predicting the frames with frequency 0, they failed at predicting the frequencies of the voiced frames. We found the source of this issue by looking at the learnt coefficients of the filters, where we saw that half of them were devoted to predict unvoiced frames. In further studies, the datasets need to be more balanced, meaning that the histograms showed in Figure 12 should be flatter.

Regarding the unison modelling, there is still a lot of work to do. In this project we presented a novel way to model a unison performance by using the mean pitch and the standard deviation (or pitch dispersion) of the mixture. We analyzed the evolution of the pitch dispersion when we increase the number of singers in the performance, and confirmed our hypothesis that the dispersion increases when the amount of singers increases. We also trained a model using these values for a very small dataset, and the results are acceptable. Again, we would need more data to build the model that could actually be used to obtain better choir singing synthesis: the amount of pitch dispersion is different depending on the voice. For example, sopranos need to sing closer in unison than basses for the listeners to hear a single pitch. This is the kind of pattern that the unison model should be able to find in the training data, so that it can be used afterwards. If we had a lot of annotated data of unison performances, we could build a model that is able to learn and generalize. In addition, there are two important aspects to take into account about this model. First, the high dispersion values that appear as a result of the timing deviations in the onsets (attacks) might be affecting the model in a way that it is capable of finding where the dispersion is very high (i.e. the attacks) but not the smaller deviations, which are the ones we are interested in; another aspect that we should test is changing the architecture: instead of using a single network with two output values we could use two networks that share the input data but have two separate outputs: the mean and the standard deviation. This should help them learn how to compute both values with more precision, because the features computed by the network will be more specific.

The next step of this project will be to improve the models by carefully analyzing them. With the constant-Q we saw that adding layers to the network did not result in a big improvement, as it just increased the accuracy for one of the datasets. At this point, we will try to better understand what is each layer doing, so that we can optimize the parameters for a better performance. Regarding the raw audio as input, there is still a lot of room for improvement: it is likely that the filter shapes are not the optimal ones for this task, and this makes the accuracies go down. Several trials with different filter shapes will allow to discover if they are already right or if we should change them. It is also very important to optimize the models: it

takes too much time for the the CNN with raw audio to make predictions, which makes it unfeasible for practical applications at the moment.

It would also be very interesting to record more singers, and obtain the pitch labels using our own pitch estimation models. These recordings are not only useful for pitch estimation tasks but also for intonation analysis, which is also an essential aspect of choir singing.

Chapter 6

Reproducibility

The main code of this project is available in GitHub with the description of each file. In the repository you will find the code to implement, train and validate the presented models, as well as the code to perform most of the steps of the evaluation presented in Chapter 4.

<http://github.com/helenacuesta/choir-pitch-estimation>

The choir dataset has not been published yet, but it will be released as part of the CASAS project. The trained models have not been added to the repository, but they will be available to download as soon as the project is completely closed.

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